

Research Article

Evaluating Theories of Consciousness

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Abstract

Consciousness is not constitutive of all matter. Rather, it only emerges from the living organization of special cells in the brains of vertebrae or in the neural ganglia of cephalopods. Possibly, all neural creatures achieve consciousness by a common mechanism.

Keywords: neuron / extracellular matrix / trace metals / neurotransmitters / tripartite

Introduction

Various Theories of Consciousness have been proposed: Higher-Order Theories (HOT) Recurrent Processing theory (RPT)- Global Neuronal Workspace Theory (GNWT) Attention Schema Theory (AST) Integrated Information Theory (IIT)

A mechanistic description of consciousness has eluded definition. A major fault of all these theories of consciousness is that they all focus on humans; none is predicated on animal consciousness or the evolution of "awareness" signaling processes of all living entities, from bacteria onward up Darwin's tree of animal evolution [1,2]. None defines the terms "information" or "emotions" in a manner that links them to the evolution of signaling processes which result in emotive neural memory. Neither do they distinguish between "awareness" and "mentality".

Our own perspective of the consciousness of neural creatures is based on a biochemical tripartite mechanism of memory. After all, without memory, a conscious creature would not long survive. The memory and consciousness of neural nets is powered by the Life Force of metabolism driven to survive. It is inherently emotive, its sensorium sensitized by molecular processes. We have proposed a tripartite mechanism which employs trace metals and NTs to encode memory, as chemographically described [3,4].

One must admit that the enigma of consciousness manifests a novel aspect in the firmament of natural forces i.e. momentum, gravity or electro-magnetism. We may never understand the force that generates conscious Life. To paraphrase the mathematician Godel:

"There are some truths that will forever remain beyond our comprehension."

Background

Consciousness is not constitutive of all matter. Rather, it emerges only from the living organization of special cells comprising the brains of ver-

tebrae [5-7], or the ganglia of cephalopods [8-11]. Possibly, all neural creatures achieve consciousness by a common mechanism which however still remains elusive to our understanding. But all modern scientists admit that consciousness is based on biochemical processes which transmute caloric energy into a realm of mentality, manifest as emotions and memory. Possibly, the linkage of emotions to memory endows experience with "meaning" crucial to survival.

So from a biologic perspective, one may well ask: *"From where does the talent of memory originate in biology?"*

There is evidence that even bacterial and single cell masses demonstrate memory by recalling past stimuli [12-16]. Some even suggest that memory resides in single cells [17]. However, to avoid lengthy philosophic puzzles, we prefer to contemplate neural creatures that demonstrate the consciousness of which we ourselves are familiar.

In that memory is a critical aspect of the consciousness of neural creatures, it was proposed that the brain employs two types of memory, the "explicit" for facts or events and the "implicit" for perceptual and motor skills. Anatomically, the former involves the hippocampus and the adjacent cortex; the latter involves the cerebellum, the striatum, the amygdala and reflex circuits [6].

But this does not clarify the mechanism whereby any kind of memory is encoded. The Connectome thesis proposed that memory is stored as anatomical changes (plasticity) in the synaptic connections which modulates the signaling strength between neurons [5,17,18]. We have pointed out the weaknesses of this thesis as it does not describe the coding of emotive states and cannot serve as a stable encoding system for persistent memory [20,21].

What drives our interest in the lives of other neural creatures? Possibly, the empathy we feel for animals derives from our resonance with their conscious experience, their thinking [22,23]. As neuroscientists, we and

others try to define consciousness as a biologic process analogous to the workings of other body organs (i.e. lungs, kidneys, blood, etc.). Earlier efforts attempted to equate consciousness to “mind, by epistemic and metaphysical arguments [24]. But these were not convincing as they were devoid of physiologic reference. More recently, [25], tried to compare various Theories of Consciousness to identify a common mechanism of consciousness, as listed below:

- **Higher-Order Theories (HOT)** - holds that being in a mental state (e.g. experience of pain) is equivalent to having a higher-order representation of oneself, i.e. consciousness.
- **Recurrent Processing theory (RPT)** - claims that consciousness occurs when there are recurrent connections, yet there is no clear-cut criterion for such recurrency.
- **Global Neuronal Workspace Theory (GNWT)** - proposes that consciousness is associated with the activation of a global network of specialized neurons that broadcast information throughout the brain.
- **Attention Schema Theory (AST)** - holds that consciousness is a perceptual attribute or inference that results from having an attention schema.
- **Integrated Information Theory (IIT)** - claims to be able to determine the level of consciousness of a given system, using a metric called ‘phi’ derived mathematically from the system’s connectivity (see Connectome).

Clearly, consciousness is a biological process experienced by all neural creatures, but by a process we have not quite figured out. Strangely, none of the above theories defines a mechanistic process that generates emotive consciousness or clarify its limits.

In general, it is presumed that the phenomenon of consciousness emerges from neural activity. [25], attempt to gain some insight by looking at where the various theories listed above stand, relative to one another. All require functions called "information" and "memory", but these terms remain undefined and their mechanism is not delineated. It is unclear how any test numerically indexes the presence of undefined consciousness in these theories. It is vague how [25], assign numerical values or design graphic schema based on such.

Evolution

A major fault of all the above-discussed theories of consciousness is that none is predicated on the thinking of animals [2,8], or the evolution of the signaling processes employed by primitive entities such as bacteria. In keeping with the trend of modern biology, an explanatory account of consciousness should explain how mentality emerged from the biochemical processes performed by single celled entities. It should follow the evolution of complex neural beings, such as mammals, from simpler entities [26,27]. Thus, we remain unsatisfied by a comparison of ill-defined “major” theories of consciousness based on only a comparison of the activities of complex human creatures.

Mentality

A confounding issue in discussing consciousness is that it that its intent is to describe “mentality” rather than “awareness”. Consciousness may be equivalent to the “awareness” of all living cells, but “mentality” is a different category of biologic talent.

For example, an entity that senses its environment and responds thereto can be considered as “conscious”. Thus, a colony of bacteria that moves to or away from a stimulus can be considered as “conscious”. The bacterial colonies have been shown to exhibit awareness and to recall that experience as memory employing chemical signals (i.e.molecules) [14]. Single cells grown in culture also respond to chemical stimuli [28]. But it is hard to assign bacteria or single cells with mentality. Rather, such consciousness

is akin to “awareness” or a “tropism”, to or away from an external stimulus, like plants.

As creatures evolved from bacteria and slime molds, they developed neurons to augment their awareness of experience and memory. They employed both electrodynamic and chemodynamic signaling modes. For example, *C. elegans* with 304 neurons [29], achieve a mental state that could recall past experience considered as emotive memory.

For our own work on memory, we consider that mentality can only be experienced by creatures with neural nets. In that context, the “information” experienced by neural creatures is inherently emotive and should be termed “cognitive information”; the memory thereof is emotive memory. Thus, a live fish could be considered as a conscious mental creature, as would an octopus, though it has no brain but a set of neural ganglia (ref). By contrast, the “information” of computers and artificial intelligence (AI) programs is “demotive”, bereft of any emotive quality and unable to encode such.

Neural mentality evolved from the bacterial signaling processes which employed molecules (termed “bio-modulators” later called neurotransmitters (NTs)) to control the movement (tropism) of the colony to or away from a stimulus source. Neural evolution continued with the development of the earliest neural creatures, the worms *C. elegans* [29]. The evolved neuron employed the same repertoire of bacterial signaling-molecules, biogenic amines, amino acids as well as new peptides (Table 1), to instigate reactions (i.e. “feelings”) to environmental stimuli. Moreover, the neurons developed a process for encoding and recalling past “feelings” which could be termed “emotive memory” (see tripartite mechanism below), thus consciousness memory.

Table 1: Neurotransmitters (NTs), which elicit both physiologic reactions (feelings) and psychic states (emotions)

Modulators	Physiologic reactions (feelings)	Psychic states (emotions)
Acetylcholine (Ac-Chol)		Anxiety
Dopamine (DOPA)	Awareness	Aggression
Epinephrine (EPI)	Breathing	Awareness
Serotonin (SER)	Blinking	Depression
Histamine (HIS)	Blood pressure	Fear
NO	Coughing	Guilt
>10 Amino acids	Crying	Hate
Nicotine (NIC)	Dilation	Heat
Muscarine (MUSC)	Drooling	Joy
> 90 Neuropeptides	Erection	Love
Endocannabinoids	Evacuation	Pain
	Fever	Sadness
Metals: Li, Ca, Co, Cu, Fe, Mg, Mn, Ni, Sr, Zn	Goose-bumps	Sex
	Heart pulse	
(Note: The metals are the core of complexes formed in the nECM), which also bind NTs) (see Figure 3,	Hunger	

Equation 3).	Itching	
	Orgasm	
	Pain	
	Salivation	
	Secretion	
	Sociability	
	Spasms	
	Sweating	
	Thirst	
	Tremors	
	Urination	
	Vasodilation	
	Vomiting	

Memory not needed need memory

In that both consciousness and mentality are keyed to emotive memory, a description of the mechanism of memory will help define the processes underlying the psychic talents of the neural net.

Tripartite mechanism [3,4]

Neural communication is based on both chemodynamic and electrodynamic signaling processes. Morphologically, the individual neurons (i.e. processors) are surrounded by a tangle of glycosaminoglycans comprising an extracellular matrix engulfing a perineural net (nECM/PNN) [27]. Among other functions, this matrix performs as a “memory material”. The neurons employ metal cations and neurotransmitters (NTs) to encode cognitive units of information (cuinfo) from which the neural circuit consolidates meaningful memory. Thus, the NTs serve as chemical elicitors and encoders of emotive states, entangling physiologic reactions with psychic states (Table 1, Figure 2).

Figure 2. Chemographic representations of the reaction of a nECM/PNN, an electron rich site (“address”) with a metal cation. The subsequent binding of a neurotransmitter (NT) to the metal-centered cognitive unit of information (*cuinfo*) confers emotive context.

Discussion

We are confronted by the puzzle of how metabolic energy is transposed in-

to subjective experience. In spite of reductionist advances in physics, quantum mechanics, information theory, thermodynamics, chemistry and biology, we are still confounded by the mystery of conscious “life”, which remains the bastion of theologians, philosophers and the God of Spinoza [30]. The gap in our understanding of life and consciousness remains wide.

The idea that consciousness is equivalent to linguistic capability is a very limited perspective that only applies to humans [31]. The words “consciousness”, “cognition” and “mentality” are equivalent terms that encompass experiences termed “awareness”, “thinking” and “emotions”. The metrics of classical physics or quantum mechanics cannot describe these realms of emotive mentality. Rather, we can only gain insight from a biochemical perspective. The neural membranes incorporate many molecular sensors such as GPCR and integrins, which in combination with neurotransmitters, operate as signaling systems (Tables 3, 4). Thus, it is simplistic to suggest that only neural connections via synaptic contacts are adequate to describe the neural code for emotive memory, as supposed by [6]. They suggest that memory involves a cascade of biochemical and cellular events through synaptic connections that seem overall too slow and cumbersome to account for the rapidity of awareness and memory (as per Equ.1).

Equ. 1. Kandel's Connectome process

Serotonin stimulus → Ca²⁺ influx → generate cAMP → glutamate release → gene activation → protein synthesis ----->memory

The energetics and kinetics of all these processes (equ.1) do not approach those required for neural memory acquisition (< 0.1 sec).

We previously critiqued the Connectome approach based on a lack of emotive signifiers [4,20,21]. Whatever the mechanism, it is apparent that neural circuits instigate a phase change of energy, projecting metabolic energy into subjective experience termed consciousness. And it must be rapid with low energy requirement.

Neural creatures of all kinds are conscious in that they think, manifest memory and experience emotions [2]. Our quest is to describe a universal mechanism of brain-induced consciousness that conforms to the biochemistry of all other organs comprising the bodies of neural creatures (i.e. liver, spleen, kidneys, etc). Some have attempted to bridge a synaptic model of memory with models based on RNA modifications [1]. Unhappily, they did not address the emotive aspects of memory or the kinetics of its formation and persistence.

We proposed a *tripartite* mechanism of memory, which involves the dynamic interactions of 3 physiologic compartments, namely:

- **neurons** – a highly extended cells with much exposed, surface. They are associated with “helper” cells (astrocytes) to aid its signaling functions.
- **neural extracellular matrix (nECM)** - the anionic hydrogel around the cells, a polymeric lattice embedding the neurons, functioning as a “memory material”.
- **dopants**-metals and neurotransmitters (NTs) ejected from neural vesicles into the nECM which encode cognitive information.

The encoded entities, referred to as *cuinfo*, are formed by the complexation of metals and NTs (dopants) at electron-rich moieties (addresses) in the nECM enveloping the neurons. They can form very rapidly (i.e. 10⁻⁷ sec for metal binding to substrate) are available at very high coding capacity (expressed in Avogadro scale (6x10²³ per liter) (16, 17), as chemo-graphically represented (Figure 3) [32-34].

Conclusion

It may be that we will never be able to satisfactorily describe all aspects of conscious mentality. Without memory, there are no emotions and vice

versa...without emotive qualities, memory fades. Mind and body are of a complex unity. Psyche emerges from the evolved physiology and chemistry of interacting neurons, transmuting an ensemble of physical sensibilities into mental qualities. Emotions and memory are linked facets of the psychic realm of consciousness, encoded and decoded by the biochemically active neural net.

Figure 4. A schematic image of Darwin illustrating his mental imaging of the evolutionary tree actuated by the tripartite mechanism of memory.

One must admit that the enigma of consciousness manifests a novel aspect in the firmament of natural forces. Its evolution from bacterial signaling and neural circuit development has been a major intellectual achievement (Figure 4). We may have identified some key components of memory processing but the driving life force that activates living beings remains impenetrable to our understanding. To paraphrase the mathematician Godel:

“There are some truths that will forever remain beyond our comprehension.”

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